

Influence of NaCl Salinity on some Aspects of Nitrogen Assimilation and Mineral Composition in Moong (*Vigna radiata* L.) Plants in the Presence and Absence of *Mycorrhizal inoculation*

V. JINDAL^a, A. ATWAL^a, B. S. SEKHON^b and RATTAN SINGH^{*a}

^aDepartment of Biochemistry, ^bDepartment of Chemistry, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana-141 004

Manuscript received 11 March 1993, revised 19 August 1993, accepted 2 November 1993

The influence of 25 mM NaCl (EC_e 3.54 dSm⁻¹) treatment on some aspects related to nitrogen (N) assimilation and mineral composition has been carried out in a pot experiment at 28 (pre-flowering stage) and 47 (flowering stage) days after sowing of Moong (*Vigna radiata* L.) in the presence and absence of *Mycorrhizal inoculation*. Mycorrhizal versus non-mycorrhizal plants results show that the former plants have greater K, Zn, Fe, plant P, total sugars and leaf nitrate concentration at both growth stages under salinity but lesser root nitrate and proline accumulation. The response of N assimilation enzymes to salinity stress varied with growth stage.

The involvement of vesicular-arbuscular mycorrhizal (VAM) fungi in improving P status of host plant is well documented. Mycorrhizal fungi are also involved in the assimilation of nitrate and ammonium ions¹. Mycorrhizal colonisation is often thought to increase stress tolerance of the host plant². VAM may enhance drought³⁻⁵ tolerance of certain plant species. Mycorrhizal fungi inoculation also improved Zn and Cu levels of host plant⁶. However, no information is available on the effect of mycorrhizal inoculation on nitrate and ammonium assimilation enzymes and related parameters along with mineral concentrations under saline environment in leguminous plants. The present work was carried out to draw comparison between mycorrhizal and non-mycorrhizal moong plants regarding nitrogen metabolism and mineral concentrations under NaCl salinity.

Results and Discussion

Pre-flowering stage : Salinity caused an increase in nitrate reductase (NR) and glutamate synthase (GOGAT) activity in roots in mycorrhizal (M) and non-mycorrhizal (NM) plants (Table 1). Leaf NR activity decreased in M and NM plants

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF 25 mM NaCl ON NR, GS, GDH AND GOGAT ACTIVITIES IN MYCORRHIZAL (M) AND NON-MYCORRHIZAL (NM) MOONG PLANTS AT 28 (PRE-FLOWERING) AND 47 (FLOWERING STAGE) DAYS AFTER SOWING

Parameter	Treatment*				SEM±
	CN	SN	CM	SM	
Pre-flowering stage :					
Root NR ^a	0.95	1.24	0.33	0.66	0.07
Leaf NR ^a	4.77	4.22	5.32	4.15	0.4
Root GS ^b	0.15	0.12	0.05	0.05	0.02
Leaf GS ^b	0.04	0.11	0.04	0.09	0.02
Root GDH ^c	1.32	1.32	1.04	1.03	0.06
Leaf GDH ^c	0.05	0.10	0.07	0.05	0.01
Root GOGAT ^d	0.82	1.05	0.65	0.90	0.04
Flowering stage :					
Root NR	0.44	0.48	0.51	0.55	0.04
Leaf NR	4.32	4.18	3.81	7.19	0.10
Root GS	0.02	0.04	0.02	0.02	0.01
Leaf GS	0.12	0.08	0.09	0.09	0.02
Root GDH	0.48	0.51	0.47	0.45	0.05
Leaf GDH	0.03	0.05	0.03	0.03	0.01
Root GOGAT	0.40	0.59	0.55	0.45	0.05

*CN = Control NM (no salt added); CM = control M (no salt added); SN = 25 mM NaCl NM; SM = 25 mM NaCl M.

^aμmole NO₂⁻ formed h⁻¹ (g FW)⁻¹. ^bμmole γ-glutamylhydroxamate formed mm⁻¹ (g FM)⁻¹. ^cμmole NADH oxidised min⁻¹ (g FW)⁻¹.

under salt stress. Root glutamine synthetase (GS) and glutamate dehydrogenase (GDH) activity was not affected due to salinity treatment while leaf GS increased. Salinity increased GDH activity in leaves in NM plants. In both M and NM plants, root nitrate concentration increased but leaf nitrate decreased with salinity (Table 2). Salinity caused proline accumulation whereas chlorophyll and plant P concentration decreased in both M and NM plants. Total N concentration increased with salinity in M plants but decreased in NM.

The results on ionic concentrations showed (Table 2) that K^+ concentration decreased due to salinity but Na^+ concentration increased in both M and NM plants. Zn and Cu concentrations remained unchanged due to salinity treatment in M as well as NM plants. Both Fe and Mn increased in M plants but decreased in NM with salinity. The comparison of M versus NM plants showed that NR and GDH activity in leaf and NR, GDH, GS and GOGAT activities in root were lesser in M plants under salinity but leaf GS activity was similar (Table 1). Mycorrhizal plants had greater total sugars, plant

P, root N and leaf nitrate concentrations whereas it was just the reverse with root nitrate and proline concentrations (Table 2) under NaCl treatment. However, chlorophyll content was similar in M and NM plants. Under salinity treatment, M plants possessed greater K^+ but lesser Na^+ concentration. The concentration of Fe, Mn, Cu and Zn were greater in M plants than in NM plants under NaCl treatment.

Flowering stage : The results (Table 1) showed that GDH, NR and GS activity in root, and GS and GOGAT activity in leaf were not affected with salinity in M and NM plants. Root GOGAT activity increased in NM plants while it remained unchanged in M plants with salinity. Salinity also increased leaf NR activity in M plants while no change in activity was observed in NM plants.

Salinity caused increase in root nitrate and N content in NM plants while leaf nitrate, total sugars decreased (Table 2). In case of M plants, NR activity in leaf and root and total N declined due to salinity, but proline, chlorophyll and plant P remained unaltered. Total

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF 25 mM ON METABOLITES AND MINERAL CONCENTRATIONS IN MYCORRHIZAL (M) AND NON-MYCORRHIZAL (NM) MOONG PLANTS AT 28 DAS (PRE-FLOWERING STAGE) AND 47 DAS (FLOWERING STAGE)

Parameter	Treatment*								SE ± M	
	CN		SN		CM		SM			
Root nitrate ^a	13.88	(0.99)	18.75	(1.89)	5.25	(1.62)	13.12	(1.26)	0.07	(0.06)
Leaf nitrate ^a	10.50	(13.50)	6.56	(5.31)	11.25	(8.01)	8.26	(7.11)	0.06	(0.09)
Leaf proline ^b	1.33	(1.40)	2.24	(1.61)	1.17	(1.16)	1.89	(1.19)	0.02	(0.02)
Chlorophyll ^c	1.10	(0.99)	0.79	(0.93)	1.02	(1.04)	0.80	(0.96)	0.04	(0.04)
Root N ^d	2.33	(3.48)	1.75	(3.89)	1.77	(5.68)	2.10	(3.00)	0.10	(0.04)
Leaf N ^d	5.25	(3.10)	4.90	(3.50)	3.15	(3.80)	4.08	(3.10)	0.12	(0.05)
Total sugars ^e	27.5	(30.62)	26.25	(25.62)	35.00	(25.00)	34.00	(34.37)	0.55	(0.62)
Plant P ^f	0.15	(0.12)	0.05	(0.08)	0.23	(0.19)	0.10	(0.16)	0.01	(0.02)
K ^g	1.7	(1.6)	1.2	(0.95)	1.8	(1.96)	1.4	(1.85)	0.02	(0.02)
Na ^g	0.4	(0.4)	1.8	(0.8)	0.8	(0.6)	1.6	(0.8)	0.03	(0.02)
Zn ^h	31	(31)	29	(28)	40	(45)	38	(42)	1.5	(1.6)
Cu ^h	15	(13)	14	(16)	19	(18)	18	(17)	0.6	(1.5)
Fe ^h	450	(669)	408	(545)	769	(671)	999	(621)	3.0	(5.0)
Mn ^h	103	(148)	87	(146)	96	(115)	134	(145)	1.9	(2.0)

*CM = Control M (no salt added); CN = control NM (no salt added); SM = 25 mM NaCl M; SN = 25 mM NaCl NM; figure in parentheses indicate data at 47 days. ^a $\mu\text{mol (g FW)}^{-1}$. ^b $\mu\text{mol (g FW)}^{-1}$. ^c mg (g FW)^{-1} . ^d%. ^e $\mu\text{g (g DW)}^{-1}$. ^f%. ^g%. ^h $\mu\text{g (g DW)}^{-1}$.

sugars increased in M but decreased in NM plants due to salinity. Potassium ion content decreased with salinity while Na⁺ increased in M and NM plants (Table 2). Zinc and copper remained unaffected with salinity while Fe declined in both NM and M plants. Salinity caused increase in Mn in M plants but no effect was observed in NM plants.

Mycorrhizal versus non-mycorrhizal results (Table 2) showed that ionic concentrations K, Zn and Fe were greater in M plants compared to NM ones under NaCl treatment but Cu, Mn and Na concentrations were similar. Mycorrhizal plants had greater concentrations of plant P, leaf nitrate and total sugars but lesser for root nitrate, proline and total N under salinity conditions. However, M and NM plants had similar content of chlorophyll under salinity treatment. Leaf NR activity was greater in M plants than the corresponding NM plants under salinity treatment, whereas root NR, GS, GDH activities were not different. There are very few reports on nitrogen metabolism in the case of NM plants. The present results (Table 1) suggest that leaf NR activity decreased in NM plants at pre-flowering and flowering stages. Similar observations were reported in case of leaf NR activity in *Pisum sativum*⁷ and *Cicer arietinum*⁸. The present results (Table 1) also indicate favourable effect of salinity in NM and M plants on root NR activity at pre-flowering stage which may be related to greater root nitrate content. Further it is well known that biological nitrogen fixation and nitrate assimilation represent major source of reduced N for plant growth and nitrogen fixation is not at its peak at pre-flowering stage but attains near the end of flowering.

Greater proline accumulation under salinity in the present results (Table 2) may increase the salt tolerance of plants by osmotic adaptation. Osmotic adaptation facilitates water absorption and maintenance of turgor and the turgor dependent metabolic processes are not affected by salinity⁹. In addition, the increased proline content of

leaves may be due to the increase in Na⁺ content (Table 2). Weimberg *et al.*¹⁰ reported increased proline content of leaves of sorghum with the increase of monovalent cations. The reduced chlorophyll content under salinity in the present results (Table 2) in NM and M plants may be related to a large decrease in plant P level which may curtail the synthesis of ATP. Earlier report¹¹ in case of *Vigna radiata* also showed reduced chlorophyll under salinity.

The present results show an increase in total N and nitrate content in NM plants under salinity at flowering stage (Table 2). The decrease in leaf NR activity (Table 1) at this stage may account for increased nitrate content in NM plants. Earlier workers reported increase in nitrate N in *Cicer arietinum* and total N in *Pisum sativum*¹² under salinity.

There is ample evidence that carbohydrates accumulate after exposure to salinity in NM plants¹³. Mycorrhizal plants also showed similar behaviour at flowering stage (Table 2) while in both NM and M plants, no effect was observed on total sugars accumulation at pre-flowering stage in the present study.

Although no reports are available regarding the effect of VAM fungi under saline environment in grain legume species but a few studies have been reported about the role of VAM fungi in the salt tolerance of plants. Improved growth of onion and bell peppers grown in saline soils has been found under inoculation with VAM fungi³. Vesicular-arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi have been found to influence the composition of amino acids¹⁴ and carbohydrates¹⁵ of the host plant. It has been suggested that in many cases the increased tolerance to salt afforded by mycorrhiza is probably due to improved P nutrition^{3,16}. However, the ability to protect the plants from salt stress was not correlated with the growth promoting effect of some VAM fungi⁵.

The present results on K and Na concentrations are in agreement with those in literature¹⁷, which reported that K concentration decreased while

Na increased under salinity. Very little is known about trace element nutrition of crops grown in saline soils. Iron and copper contents of corn and barley plants decreased while those of manganese and zinc increased with salinity¹⁸. Concentration of Mn and Fe in the vegetative parts of soybean decreased with salinity¹⁹. The present results on decrease in Fe concentrations in NM plants find support from observations reported in the literature^{18,19}. However, the present observation differed on Cu concentrations as the latter are not affected in NM plants at both growth stages. Mycorrhizal inoculation also improves Zn and Fe levels compared to that in NM plants under salinity at both the growth stages.

Experimental

Plant material and treatments : Moong (*Vigna radiata* L. cv SML-32) plants were raised in earthenware pots lined with impervious polythene sheets to prevent leaching of salts. Each pot contained 2.0 kg of 2 mm sieved, sterilised, autoclaved hyperthermic mixed, calcareous, typical Ustochrept. Fatehpur sandy loam (clay, 20; silt, 10; sand 70%) soil from the experimental farm of Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana. The soil used had pH 8.3, EC_e 0.3 dSm^{-1} , and was low in organic carbon (0.3%), low in available N (180 kg N ha^{-1}) and low in available P (4.8 kg P ha^{-1})²⁰. The salt levels were C- (control, no salt added) and S- (25 mM NaCl- EC_e 3.54 dSm^{-1}) in the presence and absence of mycorrhizae. To ensure uniform mixing of NaCl in the soil, the required quantity of NaCl was mixed thoroughly in 2 kg soil per pot and required quantity of water added to raise soil moisture level to field capacity.

The pots were then covered and allowed to equilibrate for one week before sowing. The pots were subirrigated with water containing negligible amount of salts. All the treatments were given 20 ppm of P (as KH_2PO_4) and 40 ppm of N (as urea). Ten seeds inoculated with *Rhizobium* culture were sown and after thinning,

four healthy uniform plants were maintained in each pot.

The suspension of *Glomus fasciculatum* (Thaxter Sensu Gerd) Gerdemann and Trappe spore prepared from soil containing 275–300 spores per 100 g^{21} was used for mycorrhizal inoculation. Soil (250 g) collected from the rhizosphere zone was suspended in approximately 1 lit of water. After shaking the suspension vigorously and allowing it to remain undisturbed for 10–20 s, it was passed through 25 mesh sieve and decantant collected in a bowl. The organic matter was trapped in sieve whereas the heavier soil particles settled in the bowl and both these fractions were rejected and only decantant was processed further. The decantant collected was again shaken vigorously, allowed to settle for 10–20 s and passed through 37 mesh sieve. The catch of the sieve was collected in a beaker. The amount of suspension thus collected was measured and after bubbling vigorously, 2 ml aliquot was estimated under stereobinocular microscope, which when multiplied with the total amount of suspension collected to give the number present in 250 g of soil processed. Before sowing, this suspension (10 ml-pot) was mixed 5 cm below the soil surface in pots under mycorrhizal treatments. Roots were separated from the soil and then cleared and stained²². Stained roots were analysed under dissecting microscope for percent colonisation²³. Sufficient plant material was cultivated from pots selected at random to permit three replications of each treatment at two samplings 28 and 47 days after sowing (DAS), corresponding to pre-flowering and flowering stages, respectively, for the determination of enzyme activities and metabolite concentrations.

Parameters estimation : Leaves or roots tissue (200 mg) was extracted in 0.5 M phosphate buffer (5 ml) at pH 7.5. In vivo NR (EC 1.6.6.1) activity was estimated²⁴. The assay of ammonia assimilation enzymes was carried out as described earlier²⁵. The tissue (200 mg) was boiled with distilled water (5 ml) for 10 min and nitrate content in this extract was estimated²⁶.

Proline²⁷ and chlorophyll²⁸ were estimated by reported methods. Total N was determined by micro-kjeldahl's method. Total sugars were extracted using 80% ethanol and were estimated²⁹. To determine plant P and concentration of ions, the dried plant material was digested in tri-acid mixture (nitric acid/perchloric acid/sulphuric acid : 9 : 3 : 1, v, v, v) and P was estimated³⁰. Potassium and sodium were estimated on an AIMIL flame photometer and Zn, Cu, Fe and Mn were estimated on a Techtron atomic absorption spectrophotometer.

References

1. C. PLASSARD, F. MARTIN, D. MOUSAIN and L. SALSAC in "Physiological and Genetical Aspects of Mycorrhizal", eds. V. GIANINAZZI-PEARSON and S. GIANINAZZI, INRA, Paris, 1986, p. 111.
2. U. HARTMOND, N. V. SCHAESBERG, J. H. GRAHAM and J. P. SYVERTSEN, *Plant Soil*, 1987, **104**, 37.
3. M. C. HIRREL and J. W. GERDEMANN, *J. Am. Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1980, **44**, 654.
4. J. C. OJALA, W. M. JARRELL, J. A. MENGE and E. L. V. JOHNSON, *Agronomy*, 1983, **75**, 225.
5. C. N. ROSENDAHL and S. ROSENDAHL, *Environ. Exp. Bot.*, 1991, **31**, 313.
6. V. GIANINAZZI-PEARSON and S. GIANINAZZI, in "Physiological and Genetical Aspects of Mycorrhizal", eds. V. GIANINAZZI-PEARSON and S. GIANINAZZI, INRA Publications, Paris, 1986, 101.
7. R. K. DAL and S. N. BHARDWAJ, *Indian J. Plant Physiol.*, 1987, **30**, 165.
8. B. S. SEKHON, H. S. SANDHU, K. S. DHILLON and R. SINGH, *Indian J. Ecol.*, 1987, **14**, 289.
9. M. L. BINZEL, P. M. MASEGAWA, D. RHODES, D. HANDA, A. K. HANDA and R. A. BRESSAN, *Plant Physiol.*, 1987, **84**, 1408.
10. R. WEIMBERG, R. H. LERNER and A. POLJAKOFF-MAYBER, *Physiol. Plant*, 1982, **55**, 5.
11. M. ASHRAF, *Plant Soil*, 1989, **119**, 205.
12. H. R. MANCHANDA and S. K. SHARMA, *J. Agric. Sci.*, 1989, **113**, 407.
13. R. MANUS and A. TERMAAT, *Aust. J. Plant Physiol.*, 1986, **13**, 143.
14. H. BALTRUSCHAT and F. SCHONBECK, *Phytopath. Z.*, 1975, **84**, 172.
15. R. M. AUGE, K. A. SCHEKEL and R. L. WAMPLE, *Plant Physiol.*, 1986, **82**, 765.
16. J. H. GRAHAM, *Hort. Sci.*, 1986, **21**, 1302.
17. H. R. MANCHANDA, S. K. SHARMA and R. P. MOR, *Indian J. Agric. Sci.*, 1991, **61**, 20.
18. N. A. K. HASSAN, J. V. DEW, D. KUNDSSEN and R. A. OLSEN, *Agron. J.*, 1970, **62**, 43.
19. E. V. MAAS, G. OGATA and M. J. GARFBAR, *Agron. J.*, 1972, **64**, 793.
20. S. R. OLSEN, C. V. COLE, F. S. WATANABE and L. A. DEAN, USDA Circ. No. 939, 1954, p. 19.
21. J. W. GERDEMANN and T. H. NICOLSON, *Trans. Br. Mycol. Soc.*, 1963, **46**, 235.
22. J. M. PHILLIPS and D. S. HAYMAN, *Trans. Br. Mycol. Soc.*, 1970, **55**, 158.
23. G. T. BETHLENFALVEY and J. F. YODEL, *Physiol. Plant*, 1981, **52**, 141.
24. B. G. JAWORSKI, *Biochem. Biophys. Res. Commun.*, 1971, **43**, 1274.
25. S. THAPAR, B. S. SEKHON, A. ATWAL and R. SINGH, *Plant Physiol. Biochem.*, 1990, **28**, 727.
26. D. A. CATALDO, M. HAROON, L. E. SCHRADER and V. L. YOUNGS, *Commun. Soil Sci. Plant Anal.*, 1975, **6**, 71.
27. L. S. BATES, R. P. WALIREN and I. D. TEARE, *Plant Soil*, 1973, **31**, 205.
28. M. JOHNSTON, C. P. L. GROF and P. F. BROWNWELL, *Aust. J. Plant Physiol.*, 1984, **11**, 325.
29. M. DUBOIS, K. K. GILLES, J. K. HEMILTON, P. A. ROBERS and F. SMITH, *Anal. Chem.*, 1956, **28**, 350.
30. P. S. WATANABE and S. R. OLSEN, *Soil Sci. Soc. Am. Proc.*, 1965, **29**, 677.

